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Introducing a new framework as a response to the existing challenges on road tunnel fire risk assessment.

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Fire accidents constitute the biggest threats for road tunnels during their operation phase. Therefore, these types of accidents are of primary concern for both policy makers and road operators since tunnels are considered as critical infrastructure systems of the road networks. The main focus of each safety strategy adopted is on reaching an acceptable level of safety of the tunnel for the public. Despite the efforts that established a common framework for the risk analysis of fires involving vehicles carrying dangerous goods, issued with the QRAM software (INERIS, 2021), this is not the case with the risk analysis of fires without the involvement of these type of goods. However, this aspect causes a serious gap on the goal of securing the level of safety of tunnel systems since past accidents indicate that this type of fires can evolve in serious disasters (Kirytopoulos, Mourelatos, Chatzistelios, Ntzeremes and Konstantinidou, 2024).

This presentation elaborates on the development of a new risk assessment framework, named "SIREN" in order to address the shortcomings of existing risk-based approaches concerning fire accidents in road tunnels without the involvement of vehicles carrying dangerous goods (Ntzeremes and Kirytopoulos, 2018). The analysis focuses on three axes. Initially, the definition of risk in the field of road tunnels is discussed, since the risk terminology used can affect the subsequent analysis. Subsequently, the structure of the "SIREN" framework is analysed in order to indicate how the shortcomings of existing risk-based approaches are addressed. Last but not least, the approach adopted by the framework for the evaluation of the level of safety of such systems and for this type of accidents is discussed in order to provide policy makers and practitioners with solutions that can enhance the transparency of risk assessment on road tunnel systems.

The proposed framework aims at developing a quantitative instrument in order to assess fire safety of road tunnels. To do so, it adopts an event-oriented definition of risk while it is designed following a scenario-based approach. Contrary to existing quantitative risk assessment methods that all work on a deterministic approach, the "SIREN" operates on a stochastic-based approach. By doing so, the uncertainty of important parameters of the tunnel system is taken into account highlighting its role during the risk assessment process, assisting thus the safety analyst by providing a more realistic depiction of the effect (benefit) of potential safety measures on tunnel system's parameters.

In brief, the SIREN's framework consists of four main layers following a top to bottom decision sequence (Ntzeremes, 2019). The framework begins with the stochastic analysis of the system, through which the parameters of the system that should be treated stochastically are identified. Subsequently, the criticality level of each of the above identified parameters is estimated in the second layer. Based on these results, the selection of the critical parameters that risk analysis should be focused on as well as the additional measures required in order to enhance the tunnel's level of safety is performed. Having applied the additional measures, the third layer of the framework that deals with the re-evaluation of the system is followed in order to estimate the effectiveness of the measures introduced. In last layer of the framework, layer 4, the decision process on the selected additional measures based on the comparison of the estimated cumulative diagrams for the different set of measures introduced in each case, one of which is the diagram that result from the use of the Best Available Technology approach.

Figure 1 depicts the results of an indicative case that the "SIREN" framework is applied. In this Figure, four cases are illustrated associated with its cumulative diagram. The blue line depicts the Number of scenarios (Frequencies) / Number of losses for the current situation of the tunnel. The orange line depicts the result in case the current situation fulfils the minimum requirements imposed by the European legislation. The grey line depicts the results in case current situation not only fulfils the minimum requirements but also designs its mechanical ventilation system in quicker response. Finally, the yellow line depicts the results in case the best available technology on mechanical ventilation is adopted. It should be noted that dots on the figure illustrate the deterministic results in case current approaches implemented for estimating road tunnel's risk.

Fig. 1. Cumulative diagrams

The presented framework fulfils the following objectives: (1) incorporates a plausible definition of risk, which allows a more comprehensive understanding of risk from the perspective of all the stakeholders of the system involved in the risk assessment process, (2) develops a framework that can be applied in different tunnel systems, also providing the flexibility to each country to incorporate its provisions and interests, (3) designs a method in order to handle uncertainty, and finally (4) addresses the problem of risk evaluation in the absence of absolute thresholds by the national provisions for these type of accidents by incorporating the Best Available Technology approach.

To sum up, risk analysis definitely supports policy makers and road operators to reach better informed decisions on the level of safety of a tunnel system in order to minimize potential unacceptable fire risks. Therefore, policy makers have imposed the use of risk analysis on a regular basis for securing tunnels' safety. However, the application of any risk assessment method cannot resolve all problems. This presentation will contribute to this issue by providing a risk assessment framework capable of addressing the deficiencies of current approaches while also providing the benefit of being applied to all tunnel types, while conforming to each county's regulative provisions.

References

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